

Effect by custom-made foot orthoses with added support under the first metatarso-phalangeal joint in hallux limitus patients: Improving on first metatarso-phalangeal joint extension

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hallux limitus is one of the most common disorders affecting foot biomechanics. Custom-made foot orthoses can improve the function of the first metatarso-phalangeal joint.

Objectives: The objective underlying this study was to test whether custom-made foot orthoses increased the range of mobility of metatarso-phalangeal joint in patients with hallux limitus.

Study design: Randomized, double-blinded, and clinical trial.

Methods: The study consisted of 20 participants (40 feet) diagnosed with hallux limitus. A control group and an experimental group both wore the same custom-made foot orthoses and, in the experimental group, a support element under the first metatarso-phalangeal joint was added to the orthoses. Two measurements were made with both groups: the relaxed position of the first metatarso-phalangeal joint and the maximum extension of the hallux. These measurements were made before first placing the foot orthoses and 6 months after application of the treatment.

Results: In the experimental group, the results showed an improvement of 4.5° in the relaxed position and 22.2° in the maximum extension being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) for both measurements.

Conclusion: Custom-made foot orthoses with added support under the first metatarso-phalangeal joint were proved to be an effective treatment to restore functionality of this joint in hallux limitus patients.